

SO-CHIC
Southern Ocean Carbon and
Heat Impact on Climate

White Paper:
Scientific results and recommendations from

Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°821001.

The Southern Ocean regulates the global climate by controlling heat and carbon exchanges between the atmosphere and the ocean. Rates of climate change on decadal time scales ultimately depend on oceanic processes taking place in the Southern Ocean, yet too little is known about the underlying processes. Limitations come both from the lack of observations in this extreme environment and its inherent sensitivity to intermittent small-scale processes that are not captured in current Earth system models. The overall objective of SO-CHIC is to understand and quantify variability of heat and carbon budgets in the Southern Ocean through an investigation of the key processes controlling exchanges between the atmosphere, ocean and sea ice.

Why is this important?

The Southern Ocean plays a disproportionately large role in regulating global climate by controlling heat and carbon exchanges between the atmosphere and the ocean. Rates of climate change on decadal time scales ultimately depend on oceanic processes taking place in the Southern Ocean, yet too little is known about the underlying processes. Limitations come both from the lack of observations in this extreme environment and its inherent sensitivity to intermittent small-scale processes that are not captured in current Earth system models.

The Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate (SO-CHIC) project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, aimed to understand and quantify the variability of heat and carbon budgets in the Southern Ocean. This white paper presents key findings from the final SO-CHIC Science Workshop (Oct 2024), which brought together researchers to discuss four critical themes:

- Heat and carbon air-sea flux and storage in the Southern Ocean
- Fine-scale and transient processes in the mixed layer
- Open ocean polynya events and their drivers
- Origin and fate of bottom waters globally

SO-CHIC has helped reduce uncertainties in climate change predictions by furthering the understanding and quantification of the variability of heat and carbon budgets in the Southern Ocean. This was done by investigating key processes controlling atmosphere-ocean-sea ice exchanges and through a combination of modelling and both in-situ and satellite observational approaches.

Graphical representation of SO-CHIC work

Global Energy Inventory (Forster et al, 2023)

Heat and carbon air-sea flux and storage in the Southern Ocean

The work conducted within SO-CHIC has confirmed the outside role this part of the ocean is playing for the uptake of excess heat and carbon from the atmosphere, thereby mitigating climate change very substantially. But SO-CHIC also demonstrated that the processes governing these uptakes and the subsequent transport and redistribution occur in a more complex but also more fascinating manner than previously acknowledged.

First, while the uptake of carbon and heat and their subsequent storage is driven by the same large-scale ocean overturning circulation that tends to be viewed as zonally symmetric, the reality is much more nuanced, that is zonally asymmetric. Particular oceanic regions, and especially the Pacific sector are taking up and storing heat much more effectively, while the Atlantic sector is especially important for the uptake of carbon. These asymmetries are crucial for assessing the potential impacts of these uptakes, that is ocean warming and ocean acidification, affecting marine ecosystems differently in the different sectors of the Southern Ocean. These differences emerge as a result of both asymmetries in ocean circulation and in atmospheric forcing.

Second, SO-CHIC has shown that with regard to this atmospheric forcing, storms strongly influence oceanic uptake of heat and carbon. Southern Ocean storms are particularly strong and frequent (occurring every few days, and lasting several days) but their impact on the ocean and its related fluxes to the atmosphere have not been well observed or understood. The storms rolling over the surface ocean impart significant mixing to the upper ocean. Several unique experiments using Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USVs) in SO-CHIC showed that deep, carbon-rich waters are brought to the surface during storms to drive an outgassing of CO₂ to the atmosphere (Nicholson et al., 2022). In addition, it was found that storms significantly influence sea surface temperature (SST) variability in the Southern Ocean by altering air-sea fluxes of heat (du Plessis et al., in review).

Further, work in the project found that mixed layer exhibit significantly different behaviour in response to storm events during autumn compared to other seasons of the year. Work is ongoing to investigate the cause of this differential behaviour, but the fact that stratification at the base of the mixed layer peaks during the autumn season is likely to be significant. This research is essential as it reveals how frequent, intense Southern Ocean storms drive significant carbon and heat exchanges with the atmosphere, influencing global climate regulation.

SO-CHIC provided an opportunity for collaborations between teams using drifting CO₂ buoys (CARIOCA buoy) and those using underwater gliders. During the SOCHIC cruise, the CARIOCA buoy was deployed with the glider. The buoy drifted away with the currents but the glider was piloted to follow the buoy for 50 days to collect simultaneous air-sea CO₂ fluxes and upper ocean hydrography and revealed new mechanisms for CO₂ fluxes in SO-CHIC.

This unique dataset has revealed that anomalously strong ocean carbon uptake is associated with large phytoplankton blooms near Bouvet Island (Naeck et al., in review). These iron-rich waters that supported such high primary productivity were back-tracked to show their origin was from an early sea ice retreat much further south in the Weddell Sea. Changes to sea ice condition now and in the future are therefore expected to have larger scale impacts on carbon uptake over the Southern Ocean.

Research conducted in SO-CHIC found that layers of Winter Water can be modified in summer by giant icebergs, when basal melting upwells Circumpolar Deep Water with entrained iceberg melt. This iceberg melt causes vigorous mixing, strong changes in stratification and has strong impacts on surface productivity due both to physical effects and nutrient loading.

Fine-scale and transient processes in the mixed layer

Fine-scale and transient processes within the Southern Ocean's mixed layer are pivotal to the global climate system due to their influence on heat and carbon exchange between the atmosphere and ocean including at depths. These processes govern the rate and depth of water mass mixing, which affects the efficiency of carbon sequestration and heat distribution. Understanding these dynamics is essential for accurately modelling climate variability and improving predictions of future climate change.

In response to this challenge, SO-CHIC led a state-of-the-art observational campaign in the Northern Weddell Sea to document and understand the year-round variability in upper ocean mixed layers and the interaction between the upper and interior ocean. Guided in its sampling by high-resolution modelling of the region, this highly successful field program has yielded several hitherto unknown insights into the Southern Ocean mixed layer. High frequency variability in mixed layer depths is strongly enhanced in the winter and spring months compared with the summer and autumn, implying more rapid entrainment and detrainment of water into and out of the ocean mixed layer. This underlines the importance of observing the Southern Ocean in these difficult-to-observe seasons (autumn-winter-spring) when considering problems around ventilation of the interior ocean. In common with Theme 1, many of these mixed layer changes and exchanges with the interior occur in response to Southern Ocean storms and intervening inter-storm periods, which in turn impact both surface heat and submesoscale fluxes.

SOCHIC also provided a unique opportunity for collaborations between teams using different surface and underwater vehicles to understand coupling between surface, mixed layer and interior processes. A good example of this collaboration involved the using drifting CO₂ buoys (CARIOCA buoy) and underwater gliders to study the fine-scale mechanisms of CO₂ fluxes. During the SOCHIC cruise, the CARIOCA buoy was deployed with the glider. The buoy drifted away with the currents but the glider was piloted to follow the buoy for 50 days to collect simultaneous air-sea CO₂ fluxes and upper ocean hydrography. Furthermore, a second glider was piloted in conjunction with a surface vehicle called a

Sailbuoy, collecting contemporaneous surface meteorology and ocean hydrography data across the Southern Boundary Front of the Weddell Sea.

A particular highlight of SOCHIC Theme 2 has been the use of high-resolution modelling both to guide the design of the field experiment, and to interpret the results emanating from it. In particular, Patmore et al. (2024) undertook a careful study to sample a high-resolution model field of the region with virtual glider deployments. This led to a much better quantification of sampling bias and aliasing than had been achieved in previous field experiments and provides a blueprint for the design of future field campaigns using autonomous underwater vehicles.

A further important result that has emerged is the critical role of the Southern Ocean Winter Water in controlling many of the surface layer processes. To this end, Spira et al. (2024) built a detailed global seasonal climatology of the properties of Winter Water, highlighting the importance of both sea ice formation and undersea topography in determining both the extent and properties of the Winter Water layer. Furthermore, Lucas et al. (in review) used techniques developed during the SOCHIC programme to understand the impact of meltwater from the giant melting iceberg A68a on mixing and upwelling of warm interior waters into the Winter Water layer of the Scotia Sea sector, alongside the influence of this basal melt on near-surface productivity.

The coupled climate in an Earth System model is sensitive to the ocean resolution of the Atlantic sector of the Southern Ocean. When SO-CHIC researchers shifted working from a low resolution ($\sim 1/2^\circ$ using an eddy parameterization to a high resolution ($\sim 1/10^\circ$, simulating an eddy rich ocean) in this sector, they found an improvement in the representation of the Agulhas retroflection, and thus reduce the overly active Agulhas leakage. This reduces the associated warm bias in the eastern South Atlantic, and in turn, has downstream effects on the coupled climate in the Tropical Atlantic, where the representation of precipitation and wind patterns move closer to those found in observationally based datasets.

Open ocean, polynya events and their drivers

Both open ocean events, and polynya in the Southern Ocean are critical to the global climate system because they enhance exchanges of heat, carbon, and oxygen between the ocean and atmosphere, directly impacting deep-water formation and global thermohaline circulation. In the open Southern Ocean, warming and heat absorption and storage patterns differ in the different sectors, and understanding these differences is important as Polynya allow for the release of heat from warmer upwelled deep waters, which influences regional and global carbon cycling and biological productivity. Understanding the drivers of polynyas—such as ocean stratification, wind, and ice dynamics—is essential for accurately modelling their role in climate regulation and predicting future changes in ocean-atmosphere interactions.

Zonally asymmetric increase in Southern Ocean heat content:

An additional focus has been the excess heat storage patterns across the Southern Ocean (Hague et al., 2024). A key finding of this model simulation based work is that the Southern Ocean is warming at different rates across each of the three basins. For example, we find much stronger warming in the Pacific sector south of 60°S compared to the Atlantic and Pacific. Further north (50 - 60°S) the upper 500 m of the Pacific cools, while the other basins warm slightly. This zonally asymmetric warming turns out to be a robust feature in our model, as well as in various observation-based datasets. Zonally asymmetric warming, can arise either (i) from a symmetric surface forcing acting on a zonal asymmetry in mean circulation or (ii) from a zonal asymmetry in the forcing itself. While we find that both factors are important with the asymmetry of the forcing playing a stronger role. Regarding the asymmetries in the forcing, we are able to diagnose the impact of each of these forcing agents by running sensitivity experiments. For the Weddell Sea, for instance, the Antarctic Slope Current (ASC) is especially important, since it transports relatively cold waters into the Weddell Gyre, where they mix with warmer Circumpolar Deep Water. Therefore, a change in the strength of the ASC can significantly alter the heat content of the Weddell Gyre.

Illustration of processes influencing the watermass transformation of Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) for the two main regimes found around Antarctica. In the cold regime regions (Weddell and Ross seas), the CDW transformation in subpolar gyres and on the continental shelves strongly limit the amount of heat reaching the ice shelves. In the warm regime regions (Amundsen and Bellingshausen seas), the absence of CDW transformation allows nearly unmodified warm deep water to reach the ice shelves and contributes to intense melting.

Origin and fate of bottom waters globally

Oceanic deep and bottom waters are crucial to the climate system due to their role in transporting heat, carbon, and nutrients globally. Formed in polar regions, these dense waters drive thermohaline circulation, distributing heat and helping regulate climate patterns. Deep and Bottom waters in the Southern Ocean are especially significant, as they sequester large amounts of carbon dioxide, mitigating atmospheric CO₂ levels. Changes in Southern Ocean deep and bottom water formation have the capability to impact global carbon storage and nutrient cycles, with profound impacts on global climate.

Research carried out in SO-CHIC has shown that the volume of Weddell Sea Bottom Water has shrunk by around 30% over the last several decades. This is linked to increases in northerly winds reducing sea ice export and formation in front of the Ronne Ice shelf and subsequent dense shelf water formation. This, combined with several contemporaneous 2023 studies from elsewhere around the continent showing similar declines in export potentially represents one of the largest shifts in the Earth's climate system presently occurring. WP3 climate model analysis suggests that this may be a sign of the onset of the projected collapse in dense water formation under all future climate scenarios. The change in sea ice production has also impacted the export of dense shelf water from the shelf to the Ronne-Filchner ice shelf cavity.

SO-CHIC researchers have supported the development of a 'realistic' NEMO1 global ocean model that accurately captures Southern Ocean ventilation patterns and magnitudes and implements improved deep mixing schemes. This has delivered estimates of Southern Ocean ventilation, provided new insights into the ultimate fate of exported bottom water and will form the basis for freshwater 'hosing' experiments underpinning ongoing Horizon Europe funded projects.

Through the combination of multiple national observing efforts, SO-CHIC researchers have mapped the pathways and quantified the variability of the slope currents and dense water/AABW export along the Weddell sea continental slope. These studies have established the transport timescales and pathways of connectivity between the Weddell Sea western slope current and their export pathway through the South Scotia Ridge at Orkney Passage. They have quantified their strength and seasonal and interannual variability, as well as establishing how changes in surface wind stress and large scale climate modes influence their transport and export. Other work focusing on surface export demonstrated the important role that sea ice variability has in setting the surface stratification and freshwater export of the Weddell Sea. Additionally a new satellite product has been developed combining multiple sources of satellite observations in sea-ice leads and cracks. This allows the observation of the circulation of the ice covered Southern Ocean at much higher resolution (spatial and temporal).

Final Recommendations from SO-CHIC

(1) There is an urgent need to understand how melting of ice shelves and icebergs—through both basal melting and surface runoff—affect the upper ocean mixed layers, especially as the frequency and size of icebergs are expected to rise in response to increased ice shelf calving in the coming century. These processes significantly influence ocean stratification, nutrient availability, and heat exchange, which are critical to predicting broader climate impacts. Enhanced study of these interactions will be vital for refining climate models and assessing future ecosystem responses.

(2) The project has highlighted the continuing need for high-resolution and novel observations of physical ocean properties in the Southern Ocean, especially in wintertime when measurements are fewest and the interactions between the surface layer and the interior are strongest. These observations should be guided by high-resolution numerical modelling, and support the development of physical understanding of these interactions such that they can be better modelled, giving greater predictability to future atmospheric and oceanic changes.

(3) To better understand our climate, it's crucial to study the frequent atmospheric storms in the Southern Ocean, as well as other climate extremes of the Southern Ocean. These storms play a vital role in transporting warm, moist air toward the poles, raising heat levels in the ocean's upper layers, with very large coupling between the ocean and the atmosphere. This 'heating power' directly influences how the ocean stores and circulates energy, making these storms one of the essential drivers in our global climate system. By closely monitoring these events and by better understanding their effect on the ocean and how to represent those in climate models, we can gain valuable insights into climate trends and future shifts.

(4) To advance our understanding of the global climate system, it is critical to study the complex interactions within the Antarctic Marginal Ice Zone (MIZ) - the

transitional area between sea ice and open ocean. This boundary zone is a hotspot for ocean-ice-atmosphere exchanges, regulating processes such as sea ice formation and heat flux. These dynamics influence not only regional sea ice extent and stability but also have significant implications for global ocean circulation and climate patterns.

(5) The loss of bottom water revealed by SO-CHIC and contemporary international efforts potentially represents one of the largest ongoing climatic shifts on Planet Earth. It also appears to be a robust result across models that this decline will continue over the 21st Century to the point that the lower overturning circulation collapses to half its present strength, with significant consequences for ocean circulation, heat and carbon storage. There is a strong need for the establishment of a coordinated observing system to quantify, understand and predict bottom water change. This effort should expand and consolidate current observations at the key bottom water export pathways. Critically, observations should be extended to the Antarctic continental shelf where these waters originate and where under-observed climatic shifts in sea ice, winds and ocean properties are driving present and future changes in bottom water.

(a) Number of useful measurement days (Y axis) for each calendar month that are derived from raw data acquired along 22 ship tracks. (b) Number of useful measurement days in the marginal ice zone. Yu et al, 2017

Consortium

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14017633

